

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵
06-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰
07-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05) ³¹

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 7 through 9):

Date	Title
13-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888) ³²
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777) ³³
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666) ³⁴

Base 7 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 7 crazy sequential representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{45_{10} \quad 63_7}} \\ -12_7 * ((-3_7 + 4_7)^{5_7 - 6_7}) \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{7_{10} \quad 10_7}} \\ (-6_7 + 5_7)^{4_7 - 3_7} * 2_7 / -1_7 \end{array}$$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$$\underline{\underline{-9_{10} * ((-3_{10} + 4_{10})^{5_{10} - 6_{10}})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6_{10} + 5_{10})^{4_{10} - 3_{10}} * 2_{10} / -1_{10}}}$$

Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

$$\underline{\underline{1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad 5 \quad 6 \quad + \quad - \quad * \quad / \quad ^ \quad (\quad)}}$$

Digits 1 up to 6 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$$\underline{\underline{-12 * ((-3 + 4)^{5 - 6})}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(-6 + 5)^{4 - 3} * 2 / -1}}$$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{(1 + 2 - 3) * 4 - (5^6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1 + 2 - 3) * 4 / - (5^6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1 + 2 - 3) * 4 - (5^6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(-(1 + 2) + 3) * 4^-(5 + 6)}} \\ \underline{\underline{-(1^2 * (3 - 4 - 5 + 6))}} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{6^* - (5^4) * (3 - 2 - 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{6 / - (5^4) * (3 - 2 - 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{6^* - (5^4) * (3 - 2 - 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{6^-(5 + 4) * (-(3 - 2) + 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{-((6 - 5 - 4 + 3) * 2^1)}} \end{array}$$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Identify genuine base 7 crazy sequential representations for 0000_7 up to 6666_7

Expected number of representations = $2_7 + 6666_7 + 6666_7 = 20000_7 = 4802_{10}$

Results

2208_{10} out of 4802_{10} were identified, see supplement.

Missing

Increasing 7

0521	0532	0550	0551	0553	0565	0566	0611	0616	0622	0632	0635	0645	0653	0661	0662	0664	1010	1030	1045	1052
1054	1061	1062	1100	1121	1132	1134	1135	1144	1150	1151	1152	1153	1160	1161	1166	1205	1210	1211	1214	1226
1231	1232	1241	1242	1243	1244	1246	1250	1252	1256	1261	1265	1310	1312	1313	1315	1324	1345	1346	1351	1355
1363	1364	1365	1366	1402	1403	1404	1406	1411	1412	1416	1420	1424	1426	1430	1432	1433	1434	1442	1444	1445
1456	1465	1466	1501	1502	1513	1520	1532	1541	1543	1562	1601	1603	1605	1606	1610	1615	1616	1621	1622	1626
1630	1631	1633	1643	1644	1645	1646	1650	1651	1652	1654	1655	1660	1661	1662	1664	2000	2001	2011	2014	2015
2020	2021	2025	2026	2042	2043	2110	2113	2114	2125	2131	2132	2134	2151	2152	2155	2156	2160	2161	2164	2165
2200	2201	2202	2203	2204	2205	2206	2210	2212	2213	2214	2215	2222	2223	2224	2231	2232	2233	2240	2242	2246
2255	2260	2261	2263	2264	2265	2266	2300	2301	2302	2303	2305	2306	2311	2312	2313	2314	2315	2316	2320	2321
2323	2324	2325	2326	2320	2331	2332	2333	2342	2344	2345	2346	2356	2360	2361	2362	2363	2364	2365	2401	2402
2404	2405	2416	2420	2422	2423	2425	2430	2431	2432	2434	2435	2436	2440	2445	2446	2453	2454	2455	2456	2461
2462	2464	2465	2500	2501	2502	2503	2504	2506	2510	2511	2512	2521	2522	2524	2525	2526	2531	2533	2534	2535
2536	2543	2544	2546	2551	2552	2553	2554	2555	2560	2561	2562	2563	2564	2565	2566	2600	2601	2602	2606	2610
2611	2615	2616	2620	2621	2623	2624	2633	2634	2636	3014	3015	3020	3021	3026	3030	3031	3032	3034	3035	3036
3041	3042	3043	3044	3046	3050	3051	3056	3061	3062	3064	3065	3110	3112	3113	3115	3122	3123	3125	3130	3131
3132	3133	3134	3135	3136	3143	3144	3145	3146	3150	3151	3152	3153	3154	3155	3160	3161	3162	3163	3164	3165
3166	3200	3201	3202	3203	3205	3206	3211	3212	3213	3214	3215	3216	3220	3221	3222	3223	3224	3226	3231	3232
3233	3234	3235	3236	3240	3241	3242	3244	3245	3246	3250	3251	3252	3253	3254	3255	3256	3260	3261	3262	3263
3264	3265	3266	3300	3301	3302	3304	3305	3310	3320	3321	3322	3323	3325	3326	3331	3332	3333	3334	3335	3336
3340	3341	3342	3343	3344	3346	3350	3351	3352	3353	3355	3356	3360	3361	3362	3364	3365	3366	3400	3401	3402
3403	3404	3405	3406	3410	3412	3413	3414	3415	3416	3420	3421	3422	3424	3425	3426	3430	3431	3432	3436	3440
3445	3446	3450	3451	3452	3463	3465	3466	3502	3503	3504	3505	3506	3510	3511	3512	3516	3520	3521	3522	3523
3524	3525	3534	3535	3536	3540	3541	3542	3543	3550	3551	3556	3560	3561	3562	3563	3565	3566	3600	3601	3605
3606	3610	3611	3612	3613	3614	3615	3622	3623	3624	3626	3630	3631	3632	3633	3634	3635	3636	3640	3644	3645
3646	3650	3651	3652	3653	3654	3655	3660	3661	3662	3664	3665	3666	4000	4001	4002	4003	4004	4005	4006	4010
4012	4013	4014	4015	4016	4021	4022	4023	4024	4025	4026	4030	4032	4033	4035	4036	4040	4041	4042	4043	4044
4045	4046	4053	4054	4055	4056	4060	4061	4062	4063	4064	4066	4103	4104	4105	4106	4111	4112	4113	4114	4115
4116	4120	4121	4122	4123	4124	4126	4130	4131	4132	4133	4134	4135	4136	4141	4142	4144	4145	4146	4150	4154
4155	4156	4160	4162	4163	4164	4165	4166	4201	4202	4203	4204	4205	4210	4211	4212	4213	4214	4215	4216	4220
4221	4222	4223	4225	4226	4230	4231	4232	4234	4235	4236	4240	4244	4246	4250	4252	4253	4255	4256	4260	4261
4262	4263	4264	4265	4266	4300	4301	4302	4303	4304	4305	4306	4310	4312	4313	4315	4316	4321	4322	4324	4325
4330	4331	4333	4334	4336	4340	4342	4343	4344	4345	4346	4351	4352	4353	4354	4355	4356	4360	4361	4363	4364
4366	4400	4401	4402	4403	4404	4405	4406	4410	4411	4412	4414	4415	4416	4420	4424	4425	4426	4430	4432	4433
4434	4435	4436	4440	4441	4442	4443	4444	4445	4446	4450	4451	4452	4453	4454	4455	4456	4460	4461	4462	4463
4465	4466	4500	4501	4502	4504	4505	4506	4510	4511	4513	4514	4515	4516	4520	4521	4522	4523	4524	4525	4526
4530	4531	4532	4533	4534	4535	4536	4540	4541	4542	4543	4544	4545	4546	4550	4551	4552	4553	4554	4555	4556
4561	4562	4563	4564	4565	4566	4600	4601	4602	4603	4604	4605	4606	4610	4612	4613	4614	4615	4616	4620	4621
4622	4623	4624	4625	4626	4630	4631	4632	4633	4634	4635	4636	4640	4641	4642	4643	4644	4645	4646	4650	4651
4652	4653	4654	4655	4656	4660	4661	4662	4663	4664	4665	4666	5000	5002	5003	5004	5005	5006	5001	5011	5012
5013	5014	5015	5020	5021	5022	5023	5024	5025	5026	5030	5031	5032	5033	5034	5035	5036	5040	5041	5042	5043
5045	5046	5050	5051	5052	5053	5054	5056	5060	5061	5063	5064	5065	5066	5100	5101	5102	5103	5104	5105	5111
5112	5113	5114	5115	5116	5120	5121	5122	5126	5130	5131	5132	5133	5134	5135	5136	5140	5142	5143	5144	5145
5146	5150	5151	5152	5153	5154	5155	5156	5160	5161	5162	5164	5165	5166	5200	5201	5202	5203	5204	5205	5206
5210	5211	5212	5213	5214	5215	5216	5220	5221	5222	5223	5224	5225	5226	5230	5231	5232	5233	5234	5235	5236
5240	5241	5242	5243	5244	5245	5246	5250	5251	5252	5253	5254	5255	5256	5260	5261	5262	5263	5264	5266	5300
5301	5302	5303	5304	5305	5306	5310	5311	5312	5313	5314	5315	5320	5321	5322	5323	5324	5325	5326	5330	5331
5332	5333	5334	5335	5336	5341	5342	5343	5344	5351	5352	5353	5354	5355	5356	5360	5361	5362	5363	5364	5365
5366	5400	5401	5402	5403	5404	5405	5406	5410	5411	5413	5414	5415	5416	5420	5421	5422	5423	5424	5425	5426
5430	5431	5432	5433	5434	5435	5436	5440	5441	5442	5443	5444	5446	5450	5451	5452	5453	5454	5455	5456	5460
5461	5462	5463	5464	5465	5466	5500	5501	5502	5503	5504	5505	5506	5510	5512	5513	5514	5515	5516	5520	5521
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5552	5553	5554	5555	5556	5560	5561	5562	5563	5564	5565	5566	5600	5603	5604	5605	5606	5610	5611	5612	5613
5614	5615	5616	5620	5621	5623	5624	5625	5632	5633	5641	5650	5651	5661	5665	5666	6000	6004	6005	6006	6013
6014	6016	6020	6021	6022	6023	6024	6025	6026	6030	6031	6032	6033	6034	6035	6036	6040	6041	6042	6043	6044
6046	6050	6051	6052	6053	6054	6055	6056	6061	6062	6063	6064	6065	6100	6101	6102	6103	6104	6105	6106	6110
6111	6112	6113	6114	6115	6116	6120	6121	6122	6123	6124	6125	6126	6130	6131	6132	6133	6134	6136	6140	6141
6142	6143	6144	6145	6146	6150	6151	6152	6153	6155	6156	6160	6161	6162	6163	6164	6166	6200	6202	6206	6210
6211	6212	6214	6215	6216	6220	6221	6223	6224	6225	6230	6232	6233	6235	6236	6250	6251	6253	6254	6256	6261
6262	6263	6264	6265	6266	6300	6301	6302	6303	6304	6305	6306	6310	6311	6312	6313	6314	6316	6320	6321	6322
6323	6324	6325	6326	6330	6331	6333	6334	6335	6336	6340	6341	6342	6343	6344	6345	6346	6350	6351	6352	6353
6355	6356	6360	6361	6362	6364	6365	6366	6400	6401	6402	6403	6404	6405	6406	6410	6411	6412	6413	6414	6415
6416	6420	6421	6422	6423	6424	6425	6426	6430	6431	6432	6433	6434	6435	6436	6440	6441	6442	6443	6444	6445
6446	6450	6451	6452	6453	6454	6455	6456	6460	6461	6462	6463	6464	6465	6466	6500	6501				

Missing

Decreasing 7

0523, 0541, 0545, 0564, 0565, 0611, 1034, 1051, 1052, 1100, 1101, 1106, 1123, 1151, 1162, 1163, 1165, 1202, 1204, 1210, 1214,
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Discussion

The “first integers that can not be sequentially represented under the defined operations” were identified “through brute force search” by Tim Wylie¹⁶ and published on arXiv:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
3	0	0	0
4	13	11	16
5	27	17	27
6	67	77	92
7	260	262	292
8	614	809	1192
9	3293	4570	5414
10	10958	14324	21212

Tim Wylie¹⁶ allowed “negation of an expression” during brute force search, while authors focused on “genuine crazy sequential representations”, which by definition do not allow “negation of an expression”. Nevertheless, identical “first integers” were identified:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
7	$521_7 = 260_{10}$	$523_7 = 262_{10}$	$565_7 = 292_{10}$

Note

Authors consider base 7 crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published crazy sequential representations are the shortest in existence.
- Published crazy sequential representations are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable crazy sequential representations do not exists.

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